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Research Article

FREQUENCY AND INDICATIONS OF CESAREAN SECTION: AN EXPERIENCE AT DHQ TEACHING HOSPITAL DERA ISMAIL KHAN

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Abstract:

Background: Cesarean section is a procedure which is done when spontaneous vaginal delivery is not possible. It is a life-saving procedure in complicated deliveries but its unnecessary use is a health concern.

Objective: To study frequency of cesarean section and its indications among subjects presenting to DHQ hospital Dera Ismail Khan.

Design & duration: It is a cross sectional descriptive study completed in six months duration.

Setting: Gynecology and obstetrics ward of DHQ Hospital Dera Ismail Khan.

Patients and methods: All cesarean sections and normal vaginal deliveries conducted at study hospital were selected in study group using consecutive sampling technique. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied for selection of subjects. After taking proper history, examination was done obstetrical ultrasonography and necessary laboratory investigations were done. Indications for cesarean section were recorded. Data was analyzed using SPSS software version 24.

Results: Total 758 subjects were studied. Out of them 54.1% underwent normal vaginal delivery and 45.9% cesarean section. Age range of subjects was 15-45 years with mean age of 27.4±6.8 years. Maximum subjects (66.7%) were 25-35 years old. Mostly births (75.7%) were full term. There were 78.7% multigravida pregnant ladies. Elective cesarean was done in 73.1% and emergency cesarean in 26.9%. Most common indication of cesarean section was previous history of cesarean in 65.6% subjects.

Conclusion: Previous history of cesarean section is the most common indication. It is common among multigravida mothers. Prior assessment of indications is necessary to plan mode of delivery.

Key words: Cesarean section, vaginal delivery, indications.

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INTRODUCTION:

Cesarean section is a very important and life-saving procedure where normal vaginal delivery is not possible, there is risk of maternal or fetal mortality. It is most commonly performed obstetric surgery. [1] Frequency of cesarean section is increasing all over the world with passage of time. Although it is a life-saving procedure but its un-necessary use is of great concern. [2] In previous three decades rate of C-section was 10-15%, reported by international healthcare community. World health organization in its meeting in 1985 stated that there is no justification of C-section rate higher than 10-15% in any region. [3] This procedure is associated with increased risk of morbidity and mortality so should be performed when it is clearly indicated. [4] Its indications include previous C-section, fetal distress, obstructed labor, breech delivery and failure of labor induction. Besides procedure, there are complications related to anesthesia as well. [5] In Pakistan mother and child healthcare facilities were not much developed previously which is a risk factor of increasing rate of C-section. But recently these facilities have been developed. [6-7] C-section rate is higher in developing countries like Pakistan due to lower literacy rate, poor primary healthcare facilities and poor socioeconomic status. [8]

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

It is a cross sectional study conducted in gynecology and obstetrics department of DHQ Hospital Dera Ismail Khan. It is a cross sectional study started in January and completed after six months in June 2020. All cesarean sections and normal vaginal deliveries conducted at study hospital were selected in study group using consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied for selection of subjects. Patients not given consent were excluded from study.

According to inclusion criteria all the cases admitted in ward for cesarean section and those booked in the antenatal clinic were included in study. Fetal and maternal both indications of cesarean were recorded. Elective and emergency cesarean sections both were included.

After taking proper history, examination was done obstetrical ultrasonography and necessary laboratory investigations were done. Indications for cesarean section were recorded. All data was documented in a preformed questionnaire containing information like name, age, address, occupation, socioeconomic status and educational status, number of gravida, parity, history of previous C-section and previous pregnancies outcomes. Data was analyzed using SPSS software version 24.

RESULTS:

Total 758 subjects were studied. Out of them 410(54.1%) underwent normal vaginal delivery and 348(45.9%) cesarean section. Age range of subjects was 15-45 years with mean age of 27.4±6.8 years. Maximum subjects 506(66.7%) were 25-35 years old. Mostly births 574(75.7%) were full term, 98(12.9%) were preterm and 86(11.3%) were post term. There were 78.7% multigravida pregnant ladies. Elective cesarean was done in 554(73.1%) and emergency cesarean in 204(26.9%). Most common indication of cesarean section was previous history of single cesarean in 106(30.5%) and history of two or more cesareans in 122(35.1%) subjects.

(Table-1) Characteristics of subjects in study group (n=758)

Characteristics of study group	Number of patients	Percentage	P-value
Mode of delivery			
Normal vaginal delivery	410	54.1%	0.041
Cesarean Section	348	45.9%	
Age			
15-25	224	29.5	0.052
26-35	506	66.7	
36-45	28	3.7	
Gestational age			
Pre term	98	12.9	0.001
Full-term	574	75.7	
Post term	86	11.3	
Type of cesarean section			
Elective	554	73.1	0.014
Emergency	204	26.9	
Gravidity			

Primigravida	136	17	0.005
Multigravida	597	78.7	
Grand Multigravida	25	3.3	

(Figure-1) Frequency of cesarean and normal vaginal deliveries in study group

(Table-2) Indications of cesarean section reported in study group (n=348)

Indications of C-Section	Number of patients (N)	% =N/348	P-Value
Previous single C-section	106	30.5%	<0.001
Previous ≥ 2 C-sections	122	35.1%	
Obstructed labour	8	2.3%	
Breech delivery	14	4%	
Antipartum hgorrhage APH	9	2.6%	
Post dated pregnancy	11	3.2%	
Placenta previa	28	8%	
Fetal distress	10	2.9%	
Uterine rupture	21	6%	
Other indications	19	5.4%	

DISCUSSION:

Rate of cesarean section is increasing worldwide beyond the limit specified by WHO with passage of time. Mortality and morbidity of fetus, newborn and mother is increased due to cesarean section rate above 10-15%. In our study C-section rate was 45.9%, including 73.1 elective and 26.9 emergency C-sections. C-section rate reported in Egypt has been reported as 41%, 45% and 46% in 2013, 2014 and 2015 respectively, its rate is 24.4% in Iraq and 62.1% in Iran. [9] Study conducted in Sir Ganga Ram hospital Lahore in 2013 reported C-section rate as 36% of total deliveries, out of them mostly cases were operated on emergency basis. [10] A same study conducted in Peshawar Lady Reading Hospital concluded 21.7% rate of C-section. [11] A survey conducted in Pakistan reported C-section rate of 25% in 2012-2013. Its rate

in other countries are 42.9% in South America, 32. [13] Its indications include previous C-section, fetal distress, obstructed labor, breech delivery and failure of labor induction. [14] Besides procedure, there are complications related to anesthesia as well. In Pakistan mother and child healthcare facilities were not much developed previously which is a risk factor of increasing rate of C-section. But recently these facilities have been developed. First pregnancy mode of delivery determines whether next delivery will be normal vaginal or via cesarean section. In our study 30.5% subjects had previous one C-section and 35.1% had previous ≥ 2 C-sections. A study conducted in Sir Ganga Ram Hospital showed similar results. Another study conducted in India B.S Hospital reported increased rate of C-section among those who had previous history of C-section.¹⁵ Study conducted in

Ethiopia reported cephalopelvic disproportion as a major indication for C-section.¹⁶ VBAC is not always safe due to chances of fetomaternal complications. [17-19] In our study uterine rupture was indication of C-section in 6% cases as compared to high rate of uterine rupture observed in 57% cases with previous C-section as reported by a study conducted in India. [20]

CONCLUSION:

Cesarean section is a most commonly performed obstetrical procedure worldwide associated with many complications related to mother and child. Previous history of C-section is a major indication of C-section in next deliveries. Proper mother and child healthcare services can reduce rate of C-section to much extent.

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